

HOLISTIC EVALUATION OF THE ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS OF BIPV SOLUTIONS IN EUROPE

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ABSTRACT:

BIPV is a complex product due to its double functionality, i.e. as building element and electricity generator). Therefore, its competitiveness assessment needs to be conducted at different levels. From a component cost competitiveness perspective, BIPV products can hardly compete against conventional building components except for the most competitive BIPV products, when compared to the most expensive competing conventional building solutions. Finally, a holistic evaluation of the economic competitiveness of BIPV solutions can be conducted. In this assessment, straightforward revenues linked to the production, sales and self-consumption of electricity are considered and an innovative “extra cost” approach is taken, allowing to account for the avoided expenses for a conventional building solution. Under this approach, the total revenues of ownership of the BIPV system do not cover the costs, for most reference cases, countries and business models studied. If residential BIPV roof systems appear as an attractive investment in many locations and cases, the competitiveness threshold remains out of reach for most façade systems, due to higher end-user costs and lower yields, except for a few countries that stand out thanks to particularly generous support schemes or irradiation such as Belgium, Italy or Spain.

Keywords: BIPV, competitiveness, LCOE, cost, NPV

1 CONTEXT AND OBJECTIVES

For years, building-integrated photovoltaics (BIPV) have been appearing as one of the key possible contribution of the PV sector to reduce the carbon footprint of buildings, from residential to industrial ones [1] [2] [3] [4] [5]. Especially as buildings and construction sector is responsible for 36% of final energy use in the world [6]. However, the sector remains in its infancy, with many products manufacturers, small shipment volumes and little information on the market size and possible developments. Moreover, bespoke architectural installations confined until now BIPV as a niche of both the PV and building sectors, contributing to create a blurry image of the sector, with a lack of pertinent information. BIPV products have been existing on the market for years now but few studies have identified the real attractiveness of such components and their perspectives for market development. As an innovative solution combining both the characteristics of a construction material and an electric generation unit, the value proposition of BIPV solutions can be difficult to assess. Eventually, the aim of the paper is to clarify that aspect by providing a methodological approach allowing to evaluate the unique position of BIPV solutions and the added value it can generate. Another objective of the paper is to estimate the economic attractiveness of a wide range of BIPV solutions on key European markets, under various business models. Finally, based on the developed methodology, the paper aims at providing quantified cost targets to be reached by the sector in order to be competitive, as well as a vision on the factors to be leveraged in priority to achieve these targets.

2 REFERENCE CASES AND MAIN PARAMETERS

To allow the analysis to be robust and representative of market reality, eleven reference cases have been defined based on collected data. These have been designed based on existing BIPV cases and cover a wide variety of BIPV solutions, building typologies and application areas [7].

In order to collect the required data on costs, a survey was sent to European installers and manufacturers of BIPV elements and mounting systems. This survey contained, among others, questions on the efficiency of the BIPV elements (if applicable), the cost of these elements, the total cost of installation in function of system size and

details regarding the various source of costs. This information was completed and cross-checked using the data and experience of partners the BIPVBOOST H2020 project.

3 COST COMPETITIVENESS ASSESSMENT

In this paper, what is defined as BIPV competitiveness is a holistic evaluation of costs, savings and revenues. As explained in a following section, the particularity of this competitiveness evaluation is that it is not exclusively analysed from the electricity generation point of view, but also from a building material cost point of view, to which the electricity revenues are added. Such approach is based on the idea that BIPV should be considered as a construction material before being an electricity generation source. More precisely, this will consist in an analysis of the cash flows generated by the project, allowing to obtain an estimation of all costs and revenues associated with the BIPV systems on their operational lifetime (called the total cost and revenues of ownership), and to easily evaluate if such investment is financially attractive.

3.1 Revenues

The present value of revenues is first estimated. They can be of different nature. Indeed, subsidies or indirect incentives can be obtained, in addition to the revenues coming linked to the electricity generating function of BIPV solutions. This can be summarized as follows:

$$\sum_{n=0}^N \frac{Incentives_n}{(1+d)^n} + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{Electricity\ Revenues_n}{(1+d)^n}$$

Where $Incentives_n$ is the total amount, in €, received in year n as incentive; $Electricity\ Revenues_n$ is the amount, in €, earned thanks to the generated electricity (through electricity bill savings and the fed-back electricity); N is the total theoretical number of periods during which the BIPV systems will be operated; and d is the discount rate, i.e. here the weighted average cost of capital.

Table I: List of reference cases (Notes: values marked with an * are rounded numbers; IRM = in-roof mounting; TM = tailor-made)

Description	Reference case ID	Technological system	PV technology	Surface available for the system	System surface power density*	Capacity installed*	Tilt, Azimuth	Degradation rate (year 1, year 1+)	Total end-user cost (exc. VAT)	O&M cost	Cost of alternative construction material	Electricity consumption band	Self-consumption rate	
Unit		/	/	m ²	Wp/m ²	kWp	/	/	€/m ²	€/kW per year	€/m ²			
Single family house (roof application)	SFH_a	PV tiles	Mono c-Si	50	123	6	35°; 180°	1,8% ; 0,45%	332	2	45	DC	30%	
	SFH_b	IRM system	Multi c-Si	50	159	8		1,8% ; 0,5%	208					
	SFH_c	TM solution	CIGS	50	133	7		0,7% ; 0,7%	249					
Multi-family house (façade application)	MFH	Ventilated façade	Mono c-Si (IBC)	300	154	46	90°; 90° +270°	1% ; 0,25%	684	5	80	IA	60%	
Educational building (façade application)	EB_a		CIGS	470	133	62	90°; 180°	0,7% ; 0,7%	412				70%	
	EB_b		Mono c-Si		146	69		1,8% ; 0,45%	462					
Commercial building (façade application)	CB_a		CIGS	250	133	33	90°; 270°+180°+90°	0,7% ; 0,7%	412				IB	90%
	CB_b		Mono c-Si		146	37		1,8% ; 0,45%	462					
Office building (façade application)	OB_a		Semi-transparent curtain wall	a-Si	270	25	90°; 180°	1% ; 1%	652				150	IA
	OB_b	Mono c-Si		94		25		1,8% ; 0,45%	797					
Industrial building (roof application)	IB_IC (IB_ID)	Metal roofing	CIGS	1400	129	180	0°; -	0,7% ; 0,7%	350	2	25	IC (ID)	90%	

The electricity revenues can be generated through different mechanisms. The most straightforward one is from the electricity bills' savings allowed by the installation of a BIPV system. The value of these savings for each year is valued at the compensable part only of the retail electricity price. Indeed, retail electricity prices are composed of the cost of energy, the cost due to network usage (transmission and distribution) as well as taxes, levies and fees. Each of these price items, and consequently also the total electricity bill, is composed of a fixed and a variable part (proportional to the kWh consumed). Therefore, savings on the electricity bills thanks to the self-consumed electricity are only possible

on the variable (or compensable) part of the retail price. The proportion of each part varies from one country to another and from one consumption band to another. Thus, a detailed analysis of the structure of retail electricity prices, for each country, but also for each type of consumer (households or not), has been conducted.

Concerning the electricity sent back to the grid, it can be valued differently in function of the regulation in place or business model applied. In most countries, it can benefit from a feed-in tariff or a preferential buy-back price. Alternatively, it can simply be valued at the wholesale electricity market price.

3.2 Costs

The present value of all costs linked to the BIPV system on its lifetime must then be estimated, and can be summarized as follows:

$$CAPEX + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{(OPEX_0 * (1+i)^n) + Other\ costs_n}{(1+WACC_{nom})^n} * (1-T_c) - \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{DEP_n}{(1+WACC_{nom})^n} * T_c$$

Where CAPEX is the total end-user cost of the BIPV system; OPEX₀ is the operational expenditures defined at the time of system commissioning; *i* is the estimated yearly inflation rate; Other Costs_n gathers potential applicable fees or taxes related to the BIPV system's installation and operation; T_c is the average corporate tax rate; DEP_n is the depreciation amount to be recorded in the books in year *n*; N is the total theoretical number of periods during which the BIPV systems will be operated; WACC_{nom} is the discount rate, here the nominal weighted average cost of capital. Note that in the case of a residential system, there is not depreciation nor corporate tax rate considered in the calculations.

3.3 Extra cost approach

As explained previously this economic competitiveness of BIPV solutions' assessment aims at being holistic by considering both the electricity generation point of view, but also the building material point of view. For this second aspect, an "extra cost approach" is thus taken.

This approach consists in only taking into account the part of the end-user cost that can be attributable to the active part of BIPV to conduct the competitiveness assessment. The underlying idea is that the installation of a BIPV system makes expenses associated to a conventional building envelope solution redundant. Also, these expenses would be due in any case, and can be considered as a fixed cost.

The extra cost is determined by undergoing the following steps: (1) First a breakdown of the BIPV end-user cost into its different cost items needs to be determined. (2) Then, it is necessary to determine for each cost item the share that is attributable to the active part of BIPV. For some cost items, the split between fixed and extra cost is straightforward, such as electrical design, electrical installation, inverter cost or cabling cost, which are 100% attributable to the active part of BIPV. For cost items such as planning or transport, the assumption is made that they are the same, would the installation serve a construction purpose only. They are thus considered as fixed cost. Finally, some costs are partially associated to the building component function and partially to the electricity generation function. It is the case of the BIPV module, the certification and permitting costs, the planning costs or the administrative and legal costs, which are influenced by both functions. The procedure for these partially extra costs is to assume that the share related to the energy generating function is 50%, as a more precise split could hardly be applied, except in the case of the BIPV module. In that case, a proxy is used to define the fixed part of the cost. This proxy is defined as the value, i.e. the component cost, of competing mainstream building components. In order to consider a relevant proxy, it is important to consider a building component having, as

much as possible, similar characteristics in terms of aesthetics, quality and functional contribution to the building envelope.

Overall, this approach can also be seen as a way to value the functionality of BIPV as a building component. Indeed, one could consider that this offset cost of the conventional building envelope solution replaced by the BIPV system is as a source of revenues, achieved in period 0, at the time the system is installed.

Figure 1: Illustration of the determination of extra cost based on the valuation of building's functionality of BIPV residential reference cases

3.4 Competitiveness calculation

To estimate the competitiveness of a BIPV system, all positive and negative cash flows are simulated, on a yearly basis. They are then summarized in a profit and loss statement, which allows to subsequently quantify the yearly "free cash flows" via the cash flow statement. Based on the free cash flows, the net present value of the BIPV project is calculated, by discounting all these free cash flows back to the initial year of investment:

$$NPV_{Project} = \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{Free\ Cash\ Flow_n}{(1+WACC_{nom})^n} = -I + \sum_{n=1}^N \frac{Free\ Cash\ Flow_n}{(1+WACC_{nom})^n}$$

Where Free Cash Flow_n of the BIPV project going to the organization who made the investment (also assumed to benefit from electricity revenues), in year *n*. Also, I is the initial investment, which, under the extra cost approach equals the total end-user cost times the estimated share of these costs due to BIPV's active characteristic.

Ultimately, the competitiveness of the BIPV project, expressed in €₂₀₂₀/m², is obtained by dividing the NPV of the project by the surface occupied by the BIPV system. This comprehensive, simplified, metric can help facilitate decision-making processes. If positive, it means that the BIPV project is economically attractive, as its owner/user earns money for every m² installed. On the contrary, if this number is negative, investing in such system is not economically attractive as it will cost more money than it will allow to earn on the lifetime of the system. In other words, this holistic competitiveness metric can help answering this question: is it worth investing in such "active" construction material, compared to a competing conventional building envelope solution?

3.5 Discount rate for BIPV systems

In the case BIPV systems are installed on residential buildings, a discount rate of 2% is applied.

In the cases where the BIPV investment is made by a company, such as for educational, office and commercial buildings' reference cases, the approach is a bit more complex. The cost of debt is estimated at 3% on average, for all tested countries. The cost of equity is estimated by approximating the asset risk of a BIPV system. This approximation is obtained by averaging the typical asset risk considered for real estate assets and renewable energy assets in Western Europe. From this asset risk, the unlevered cost of equity is calculated for each country, using the capital asset pricing model. Also, the debt ratio $D/D+E$ is estimated at 0,5, for all tested countries. Eventually, the WACC is calculated using the following equation:

$$WACC_{nom} = r_A - \frac{D}{D+E} * T_c * r_D \left(\frac{1+r_A}{1+r_D} \right)$$

Where D is the amount of debt used; r_D is the cost of debt; T_c is the average corporate tax rate, which is country-specific; E is the amount of equity used; r_A is the unlevered cost of equity.

Eventually, the calculated nominal WACC per country are as follows:

Table II: Estimated nominal WACC per country for BIPV

	BE	CH	DE	FR	IT	NL	SP
WACC (nom.)	5,3 %	5,1 %	4,9 %	5,2 %	7,4 %	5,2 %	6,0 %

4 COMPETITIVENESS RESULTS

For each of the seven studied countries, the business model applicable at the end of 2019, according to the local regulation, for a specific segment of installed nominal capacity, is tested. If more than one business model is applicable, the one yielding the best results is displayed in the following charts. An additional indicator to the competitiveness presented in the previous section is used: the modified internal rate of return (MIRR) of the project. Its value can then be compared to the discount rate used in each case to support or nuance the competitiveness results. For various reference cases, the payback times are also provided. A summary of used abbreviations is provided below.

Table II: Business models abbreviations

Abbreviation	Complete labelling
FIT	Feed-in tariff
FIP	Feed-in premium
GC	Green Certificate
MP	Market Premium
NB	Net-billing
NM	Net-metering
P	Premium
SDE	SDE Contribution
W	Wholesale market price

Figure II: Competitiveness results for the three residential BIPV roofing systems.

The three different residential BIPV roofing technologies (solar tiles based on mono c-Si (SFH_a), in-roof mounting system based on multi c-Si (SFH_b) and tailor-made BIPV solution based on CIGS (SFH_c)) show similar competitiveness patterns across countries, with values lying close to or above the competitiveness threshold. The highest competitiveness values are reached for the SFH_b, with the competitiveness threshold reached in all seven countries. The net-billing scheme in Italy and to a lesser extent the net-metering business model in Belgium and in the Netherlands, yield the highest competitiveness. Satisfactory competitiveness values are also reached in Germany, France and Switzerland under the (feed-in) premium/tariff business models. In Spain, even though the injected electricity can only be valued up to the wholesale market electricity price, advantageous solar irradiance conditions allow for attractive results for roofing systems. As far as the MIRR Project is concerned, when the competitiveness threshold is reached, the associated MIRR project is significantly higher than the considered nominal discount rate of 2%.

Figure III: Competitiveness results for the residential BIPV façade cladding systems.

The investigation of a residential BIPV system for a multifamily housing, i.e. façade cladding with insulation, based on mono c-Si (interdigitated back contacts solar cells), results in very low competitiveness values overall.

Figure IV: Competitiveness results for the two educational building reference cases.

As far as educational building's reference cases are concerned, with the exception of Belgium, the competitiveness threshold is never reached. Indeed, the Green Certificate scheme in Belgium offers a very profitable remuneration which adds to an already relatively high feed-back value, at the wholesale market price, compared to other countries. In addition, for educational buildings, the considered IA consumption band still allows for generous savings on the electricity bill, especially since in this case a self-consumption rate of 70% is considered. The net-metering in Italy or the feed-in premium in Switzerland or the wholesale market business model in Spain are close to reaching the competitiveness threshold. Indeed, all three countries have quite high compensable retail electricity prices, thus allowing comfortable savings on the electricity bill.

Figure V: Competitiveness results for the two office building reference cases.

Competitiveness results for semi-transparent curtain walls based on a-Si and mono c-Si PV technologies on an office building, have plummeted towards values between -150 and -450 €/m² and the payback times are always longer than the system lifetime. Particularly low values are

reached for the reference case OB_a, based on a-Si for which very low efficiency values apply.

Figure VI: Competitiveness results for the two commercial building reference cases.

Concerning the commercial building's reference cases, there are a lot of similarities with the EB_a and EB_b reference cases, with Belgium being the only economically attractive case. Although, because the considered electricity consumption band is IB, lower retail electricity prices apply thus diminishing the savings on the electricity bill. This price gap between the IA and IB consumption band is particularly notable in Spain, as retail electricity prices drop by 100% from one consumption band to another.

Figure V: Competitiveness results for the two industrial building reference cases.

The reference case focusing on an industrial building is based on a BIPV roof application thus allowing higher yields, lower costs and therefore better competitiveness results than in the other non-residential BIPV reference cases, based on facade applications. Nevertheless, two main factors lead to mitigated results. First, the building occupant is assumed to be a heavy consumer, therefore, retail prices of electricity lies in the IC or ID consumption band. Hence, these prices are quite low and savings on the electricity bills are limited, even though the self-consumption rate is set to 90%. Indeed, slightly better results can be observed when the IC consumption band is

considered. Secondly, the high considered self-consumption rate (90%) implies that only a small amount of electricity is fed back to the grid. Hence, it is not possible to fully take advantage of potentially attractive feed-back electricity remuneration's schemes. In Germany, the capacity limit of 100 kW which applies to be entitled a feed-in tariff is reached for this studied reference case (with a 180 kWp installed capacity).

5 CONCLUSIONS

Because of their multifunctionality, BIPV competitiveness can and should be studied through various aspects. From a component or system cost competitiveness perspective, BIPV products can hardly compete against conventional building envelope solutions, except for the most competitive BIPV products.

The holistic competitiveness assessment of BIPV has led to multiple conclusions. Competitiveness results are highly dependent on the compensable retail electricity prices and the support schemes existing in each studied country. It is also closely tied to investors' consumption profiles. In Belgium, for example when the "green certificate"-based business model is considered for commercial buildings or in Italy, when the net-billing scheme applies for residential cases, positive competitiveness values are reached. On the contrary, in the remaining countries, a combination of unfavourable factors (low irradiance conditions, low compensable retail prices), such as the Netherlands, leads to the competitiveness threshold rarely being achieved

When investigating roof BIPV systems integrated to residential housing, BIPV products already can be considered in many cases as an attractive investment. Yet, when façade integrated BIPV systems are evaluated, the attractiveness is less straightforward, with the exception of a few countries in which the irradiation conditions and/or the support schemes are particularly favourable. This is due to the fact that façade integrated BIPV systems are on average more expensive and benefit from less optimal irradiation conditions than roofs.

Nevertheless, BIPV should not be looked at as a main source of income but as a supplementary investment offering reasonable pay back periods. This mitigates some of the negative competitiveness results presented here. In addition, as the BIPV market develops, total end-user costs will decrease. In addition, other technical parameters will also be positively impacted by the technology's maturity increase. Indeed, higher module efficiency, lengthened system lifetime will significantly contribute to improve the competitiveness results [8].

Then, the introduction of innovative business models increasing the possibilities of PV electricity's valuation, e.g. by allowing the selling of electricity to neighbours or increasing self-consumption by reducing the mismatch between electricity consumption and production will also contribute to enhance competitiveness.

Finally, the green image carried by BIPV products or the unique aesthetical aspect associated to buildings integrating BIPV can also be considered as additional values which could be translated into additional cashflows, in some specific cases. Indeed, such buildings could potentially be rent or sold at higher prices and could benefit from an enhanced attractiveness. BIPV could also be considered a cost-efficient solution to reaching nZEB primary energy balance or renewable energy systems' installation requirements, in some cases [9].

All of these further aspects of BIPV are difficult to quantify and to model as part of reference cases, as there is strong dependency to local project's conditions. Overall, it is important to insist on the fact that a case by case analysis needs to be conducted in order to assess relevantly and precisely the economic attractiveness of BIPV projects.

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